

Wrist Angle Measurement Using Wearable Inertial Sensors

(Pengukuran Sudut Sendi Pergelangan Tangan Dengan Menggunakan Penderia Inersia Boleh Dipakai)

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ABSTRACT

Human motion analysis is widely used in many fields such as physical rehabilitation, athlete training, health status diagnosis and others. Wrist joint movement analysis is important because we need our hands to conduct daily works such as driving, eating, writing and others. But the existed equipment or system can only be used to analyze the wrist joint movement by trained personnel such as physicians or therapists. The problems in using the IMU are the computational problems for determining the angle and the effect of offset errors on gyroscope's output as a gyroscope provides rate of rotation and integration of its output is needed to determine the amount of an object's rotation. The objective of this research is to develop a system using one Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) to analyze the wrist joint movement and develop an app to display the data. In this research, a system had developed to measure the wrist joint angle using wearable sensors. The wearable sensor we used is an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) which is Intel CurieNano to measure the wrist joint angle. Intel CurieNano combines 3-axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope was used as a sensor. The data from 3-axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope were combined using data fusion algorithm which is complementary filter to get the joint angle. The data is sent from IMU to the app through Bluetooth. The app displayed the data in numerical and graphical form. The IMU is used to measure some certain angles such as 10°, 30°, 60° and 90°, and the correlation coefficient is 0.9972. The wrist joint angle is measured using the system and compared the data with goniometer to determine the accuracy of the system. This system is able to achieve 94% of accuracy compared to goniometer.

Keywords: Wearable Sensor; IMU; App; Wrist Joint Angle; Complementary Filter

ABSTRAK

Analisis pergerakan manusia boleh digunakan dalam beberapa bidang seperti rawatan rehabilitasi, latihan atlet, diagnosis taraf kesihatan dan sebagainya. Pergerakan sendi pergelangan tangan amat penting kerana pergerakan sendi pergelangan tangan banyak membantu kita dalam kegiatan kehidupan harian seperti makan, memandu, bertulis dan sebagainya. Tetapi, sistem atau alat yang sedia ada seperti goniometer susah untuk menganalisis pergerakan sendi pergelangan tangan kerana sistem atau alat tersebut sukar dijalankan tanpa nasihat pihak yang berkaitan. Masalah menggunakan IMU untuk mendapatkan sudut adalah masalah-masalah pengiraan dan kesan mengimbangi ralat di output giroskop apabila giroskop memberikan kadar putaran dan integrasi outputnya diperlukan untuk menentukan jumlah putaran satu objek. Objektif penyelidikan ini adalah untuk membangunkan satu sistem yang menggunakan satu unit ukuran inersia (IMU) untuk menganalisis pergerakan sendi pergelangan tangan, dan membangunkan satu app. Dalam penyelidikan ini, satu sistem telah dibangunkan untuk menganalisis sudut sendi pergelangan tangan. Penderia yang boleh dipakai yang digunakan dalam penyelidikan ini adalah unit pengukuran inersia iaitu Intel CurieNano yang bersepadu dengan 3 paksi meter pecut dan 3 paksi giroskop. Selain itu, satu algoritma gabungan data penderia iaitu Turas Complementary telah digunakan untuk menggabungkan data mentah dari 3 paksi meter pecut dan 3 paksi giroskop untuk menganalisis sudut sendi pergelangan tangan. Data dari IMU dihantar kepada app tersebut melalui Bluetooth. Data tersebut dipamerkan di app tersebut dalam bentuk graf dan berangka. IMU digunakan untuk menganalisis beberapa sudut seperti 10°, 30°, 60° dan 90° untuk menguji ketepatan IMU dan pekali kolerasi adalah sebanyak 0.9972. Sudut sendi pergelangan tangan diukur dengan sistem tersebut dan berbanding dengan goniometer untuk menguji ketepatan sistem ini. Sistem ini dapat mencapai 94% daripada ketepatan berbanding dengan goniometer.

Kata kunci: Penderia yang boleh dipakai; IMU; App; Sudut Sendi Pergelangan Tangan; Turas Complementary

INTRODUCTION

The movement of the upper limb is integral in preserving the balance and function of the human body. One of the important anatomical structure of the upper limb is the wrist joint. The wrist joint is a complex joint comprises of carpal, radius and ulna bones together with ligaments, volar and overlying smooth muscles. Wrist joint which connected to the hands is important to human as it is used to conduct daily works such as driving, writing and others at most of the times. There are 4 types of wrist joint movement such as flexion, extension, radial deviation and ulnar deviation (Ryu et al. 1991). Extension and flexion angles can be used to determine the range of motion of the wrist. Wrist extension is the movement of raising the back of the hand towards the back of the forearm while wrist flexion is the movement of bending the palm down. Range of motion is the distance and direction of a joint that can be moved to its maximum capacity. The range of motion for a normal wrist joint is 150° where the flexion angle is 80° and extension angle is 70° (Trejo et al. 2017). Many factors can affect the range of motion of the wrist joint such as age, gender, daily activities and tissue deterioration (Than et al. 2012). Any disruption to any anatomical structures of the wrist joint will impair the overall function and range of motion of the hand namely conditions such as fracture, carpal tunnel syndrome, stroke and many others. Joint angle measurement which is normally carried out in clinic or hospital to measure the range of motion commonly used a goniometer apparatus. Although this apparatus is widely used to measure the joint angle movement, it requires a trained personnel such as physiotherapist to operate the instrument (Trejo et al. 2017).

On the other hand, wearable technology is a technology that can be worn by a person to obtain or record info regarding of the user. Normally, wearable technology has sensors that can be used to track motion, monitor personal health condition, and others. Nowadays, wearable technology is very popular in medical field especially the application that related to health monitoring. For example, some devices that include wearable technology such as Mi band, Fitbit can be worn by user to measure heartbeat rate, measure the running speed, monitor sleep quality, step counter and others (Sandall 2016).

Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) is considered as one of a wearable technology and normally it consists of tri-axis accelerometer and tri-axis gyroscope (Nwaizu et al. 2016). There are many types of IMU in the market such as MPU6050 consists 6 degree of freedom (DOF) IMU, MPU9150 consists of 9 DOF IMU and others (Desa et al. 2009). Accelerometer is a device or sensor that can measure acceleration while gyroscope can measure angular velocity. But there is limitation for both accelerometer and gyroscope. Accelerometer is

very accurate only if the accelerometer stays in stationary while the gyroscope is accurate in short term only (Long Tran 2017).

According to Akintade’s and Kehinde’s research, they used two different inertial sensors such as gyroscope and accelerometer to measure the knee joint angle and compare the data of these two different inertial sensors. From their research, they concluded that the accelerometer is good in measuring stationary angle while gyroscope is effective in measuring angle if there is any movement of gyroscope (Akintade & Kehinde 2015).

Nwaizu built a system that can be used to measure the knee joint angle with two accelerometers that placed on shank and thigh. In his research, he introduced three ways to measure knee joint angle. In the first method, two accelerometers were worn around the elbow joint. The formula to calculate the angle is shown in Equation (1).

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{ax_2ay_1 - ax_1ay_2}{ax_1ax_2 - ay_1ay_2} \tag{1}$$

where the acceleration in x and y axis in the both accelerometers are represented as (ax1, ay1) and (ax2, ay2). The second method is to find the knee joint angle by subtracting the angle measured on thigh with the angle measured on shank. The last method is to calculate the joint angle between two accelerometers. The formula to calculate the joint angle is shown in Equation (2)

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{axbx + ayby + azbz}{\sqrt{ax^2 + ay^2 + az^2} \sqrt{bx^2 + by^2 + bz^2}} \tag{2}$$

where the acceleration in x, y and z axis in both accelerometers are represented as (ax, ay, az) and (bx, by, bz). In his study, the angle measured using method two gives a better accuracy as it gives the nearest angle to the angle measured using goniometer (Nwaizu et al. 2016).

Bennett used Artificial Neural Network (ANN) technique to estimate the knee joint angle using the data obtained from accelerometer and gyroscope from two IMUs where the IMUs are placed on thigh and shank. In his research, data is collected from a person who takes 50 steps in walking with constant speed. Then the data obtained is used to train and test the performance of ANN. In his research, he concluded that ANN can used to estimate the knee joint angle with a 0.97 correlation and a 3.8 degrees root mean square error (Bennett et al. 2013).

Jakob also used accelerometer and gyroscope to measure the flexion and extension of knee joint angle. He placed two IMUs on shank and thigh respectively. He used Extended Kalman Filter to combine the data of gyroscope and accelerometer to overcome the drift problem of gyroscope (Jakob et al. 2013).

However, the problems in using IMU are computational problems for determining the angles also, the effect of offset errors on gyroscope's output as a gyroscope provides rate of rotation and integration of its output is required to determine the amount of rotation (Nwaizu et al. 2016).

The aim of this project is to develop a system that can be used to measure wrist joint movement using a wearable sensor with an app to receive the data from IMU through Bluetooth. The app is built to display the data in numerical and graphical form. Besides that, the wrist joint angle is measured using the system and goniometer and compared the data to determine the accuracy of the system.

METHODOLOGY

In this research, hardware that involved is an Intel CurieNano and a computer while the software that involved are Arduino IDE 1.8.5 and MIT App Inventor 2. An Intel CurieNano is used as a 6 degree of freedom (DoF) IMU which is placed on the back of the hand to measure the wrist joint angle. MIT App Inventor 2 is used to build an app that can receive data from IMU through Bluetooth and display the data in numerical and graphical form.

Hardware Aspect

An Intel CurieNano is used as a 6 degree of freedom (DoF) IMU which consists of a tri-axis gyroscope and a tri-axis accelerometer to measure the wrist joint angle. The 6 DoF IMU is used as a sensor because the wrist joint angle is measured by fusing the tri-axis accelerometer and tri-axis gyroscope. Figure 1 shows the Intel CurieNano.

FIGURE 1. Intel CurieNano

The gyroscope is used to measure the angular velocity while the accelerometer is used to measure the acceleration. The raw data from accelerometer and gyroscope are used to calculate the pitch angle. The formula used to calculate the pitch angle from accelerometer and the formula to calculate the pitch angle from gyroscope are shown in Equation (3) and (4) respectively where a_{ix} , a_{iy} , a_{iz} and w are the raw acceleration in three axis and raw data from gyroscope respectively.

$$\theta = \sin^{-1} \frac{a_{iy}}{\sqrt{a_{ix}^2 + a_{iy}^2 + a_{iz}^2}} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi = \int w \, dt \quad (4)$$

Since accelerometer can only measure the angle of an object while the object is in static but when the object is moving, the angle will become inaccurate. In order to solve this problem, the pitch angle of gyroscope and accelerometer are combined using complementary filter to obtain the tilted angle. A complementary filter takes the advantages of the sensors and compensates the disadvantages of the sensors. The formula for the complementary filter to measure the tilted angle is shown in Equation (5).

$$\varphi = 0.9 \times (\varphi + \phi) + 0.1 \times \theta \quad (5)$$

Software Development

An app is built to display the data in numerical and graphical form. The IMU is built in with a Bluetooth module which is Bluetooth 4.0 that can transmit data within a short range. Bluetooth 4.0 is also known as Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) which consumes a very low power. A maximum 20 bytes can be sent with each BLE transmission. A float takes up 4 bytes, so 4 bytes of memory space will be shared with an array of 4 unsigned characters. In this research, only a float will be sent from IMU to app, so the data can be sent with 4 bytes. The app will connect with the IMU and the data will send from IMU to app through BLE. Figure 2 shows the flow chart of the app.

FIGURE 2. Flow chart of app

Calibration and Validation test

The IMU sensor is placed on the back of the hand to carry out the wrist joint angle measurement. Before measurement, calibration process needs to be done. The user is required to place his/her hand at a fixed position for a few seconds to carry out calibration. Figure 3 shows the position of hand while calibration process takes place. Make sure the hand is in stationary and stable condition.

FIGURE 3. Position of the hand while calibration

The IMU sensor is used to measure some angles such as 10°, 30°, 60° and 90° for over ten trials to determine the accuracy of the IMU sensor. A linear regression relation between the IMU angle and protractor angle is plotted to determine the regression relation between IMU angle and protractor angle.

Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) is used to measure the distance between Bluetooth devices. The relationship between the distance and Bluetooth RSSI was tested in a room. An iPhone was used to measure the Bluetooth RSSI from the IMU sensor in a room. A total of 5 samples are measured from 0 to 60 cm at 10 cm intervals.

Preliminary test

For validating of the wrist joint angle measurement using IMU sensor, a traditional instrument such as goniometer is used to measure the actual angle of the wrist joint. Figure 4 and 5 show the extension and flexion angle measurement using IMU while Figure 6 and 7 show the extension and flexion angle measurement using goniometer. 3 volunteers were examined to determine the extension and flexion angles using IMU and goniometer over 3 trials. The wrist joint angle measured using IMU and goniometer is compared.

FIGURE 4. Extension angle measurement using IMU

FIGURE 5. Flexion angle measurement using IMU

FIGURE 6. Extension angle measurement using goniometer

FIGURE 7. Flexion angle measurement using goniometer

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A wearable sensor system is developed which consists of an IMU to measure the wrist joint angle and an app to display the data in graphical and numerical form.

Hardware Aspect

The system is able to measure tilted angle using IMU. The measured titled angle is shown in Figure 8.

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COM3 (Arduino/Genuino 101)
| Angle - 54.43
| Angle - 55.18
| Angle - 55.85
| Angle - 56.42
| Angle - 56.96
| Angle - 57.47
| Angle - 57.88
| Angle - 58.29
| Angle - 58.65
| Angle - 59.04
| Angle - 59.43
| Angle - 59.76
| Angle - 60.07
| Angle - 60.31
| Angle - 60.56
| Angle - 60.77
    
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FIGURE 8. Measured titled angle

Software Development

An app is built and is shown in Figure 9. This app can be connected up to 2 Bluetooth devices at a time. A text file can be created by typing a name at the textbox. The incoming data are stored in the text file. The Bluetooth device can be shown by pressing the "Connect" button. The Bluetooth device list is shown in Figure 10. Once the app is connected with the IMU, the data is sent from IMU to app through BLE. The data are displayed in numerical and graphical form.

FIGURE 9. Data displayed in app

Calibration and Validation Test

The IMU is used to measure some angles such as 10°, 30°, 60° and 90° over ten trials to test the accuracy of the IMU. Results are shown in Table 1. The effect of drift is eliminated by forcing the output of the gyroscopes to zero. Therefore, the data will not drift when the IMU stays in stationary. The percentage differences of the data obtained were used to determine the precision of the angle. The average percentage difference between IMU angle and protractor angle is less than 7%. Figure 11 shows the liner regression relation between IMU angle and protractor angle. The correlation coefficient is 0.9972. A very high positive correlation coefficient shows a very good positive relation between IMU angle and protractor angle.

FIGURE 10. List of Bluetooth devices

TABLE 1. Angle measured using IMU over ten trials

Trials	10°	30°	60°	90°
1	11.28	32.62	63.74	86.99
2	11.12	32.65	63.73	86.99
3	11.12	32.64	63.72	87.00
4	10.97	32.63	63.70	87.01
5	10.90	32.63	63.68	87.00
6	10.85	32.62	63.68	87.00
7	10.76	32.58	63.67	86.98
8	10.69	32.58	63.66	86.97
9	10.61	32.58	63.65	86.99
10	10.56	32.57	63.65	86.98
Mean	10.886	32.610	63.688	86.992
Percentage differences	8.86%	8.7%	6.15%	3.34%

FIGURE 11. Linear regression relation between IMU angle and protractor angle

The Bluetooth RSSI values were measured from 0 to 60 cm. The result of this test is shown in Figure 12. The average RSSI values from 0 to 60 cm are -45, -53.8, -61.6, -69, -72.8, -77.8, and -85.8

dBm. According to Figure 12, the RSSI value increases in negative direction as the distance between the IMU sensor and iPhone increases.

FIGURE 12. Relationship between RSSI values and distance

Preliminary test

Table 2 shows the flexion and extension angle measurement using IMU and goniometer of three volunteers. Table 3 shows the average flexion and extension angle measurement using IMU and goniometer of three volunteers. The wrist extension and flexion angles measured by IMU are almost the same as the angles measured using goniometer. The average wrist

extension angle difference between goniometer and IMU is just 1.445° while the average wrist flexion angle difference is just 4°. The wrist joint angle measured using IMU sensor is able to achieve 94% of accuracy compared to goniometer. Figure 13 shows the data analysis in graphical form using Matlab. From figure 16, the value increases from 0.958° to 69.12° is the extension movement while the value increases from -2.93° to -79.7° is the flexion movement.

TABLE 2. Flexion and extension angle measurement using IMU and goniometer of three volunteers

Volunteer	Movement	Angle (IMU)				Angle (Goniometer)				Error (%)
		1	2	3	Average	1	2	3	Average	
1	Extension	72	76	74	74	70	70	70	70	5.71
	Flexion	-78	-77	-74	-76.333	80	85	80	81.667	6.53
2	Extension	55	60	66	63.333	60	65	65	60.333	4.74
	Flexion	-86	-86	-78	-82	85	85	80	83.333	2.00
3	Extension	48	52	55	51.667	55	45	45	48.333	6.90
	Flexion	-71	-64	-69	-68	70	75	75	73.333	7.27

TABLE 3. Angle comparison between goniometer and IMU

Movement	Goniometer	IMU	Error (%)
Extension	60.555°	62.000°	2.386
Flexion	79.444°	75.444°	5.035

FIGURE 13. Data analysis in graphical form using Matlab

CONCLUSION

A system used to analyze the wrist joint movement is developed. This system can be used to measure the wrist extension and flexion angles using IMU. The IMU sensor is used to measure certain angles such as 10°, 30°, 60° and 90° to test the accuracy of the IMU sensor and the correlation coefficient is 0.9972. An app is developed to connect to the IMU sensor using Bluetooth. The wrist extension and flexion angles measured using IMU sensor are sent to the app and displayed the data in the app in numerical and graphical form. The wrist extension and flexion angles were measured by goniometer and this system and the both results were compared. The wrist joint angle measured using this system can achieve 94% of accuracy compared to goniometer.

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